

YOUTH MEDIA LITERACY IN THE DIGITAL AGE: THE ROLE OF VLOGGING IN IMPROVING ENGLISH SPEAKING SKILL

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Abstract. *It is universally acknowledged that social media plays a large role and there are many potential benefits in the lives of the present generation. Therefore, it is essential to utilize this platform as an educative tool, particularly in the field of language learning. Language acquisition can be easy and entertaining with the help of social networks as it promotes collaborative learning. Vlogging is a popular and influential media for learners. It is a tool that helps students to create an interesting learning process through video blog. This academic paper aims to describe how vlogs are implemented to develop speaking skills and the effectiveness of using vlogs in learning English. The findings concluded that most students were interested in using social media to improve their English speaking skill.*

Key words: *Video blog, vlogging, speaking skill, social media, media literacy.*

МЕДИЙНАЯ ГРАМОТНОСТЬ МОЛОДЕЖИ В ЦИФРОВУЮ ЭПОХУ: РОЛЬ ВИДЕОБЛОГИНГА В РАЗВИТИИ НАВЫКОВ УСТНОЙ РЕЧИ НА АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ

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Аннотация. *Общеизвестно, что социальные сети играют большую роль и приносят множество потенциальных преимуществ в жизни современного поколения. Поэтому крайне важно использовать эту платформу в качестве образовательного инструмента, особенно в сфере изучения языков. Освоение языка может быть лёгким и увлекательным с помощью социальных сетей, так как они способствуют совместному обучению. Videоблогинг является популярным и влиятельным медиаформатом для учащихся. Это инструмент, который помогает студентам создать интересный процесс обучения через видеоблоги. Цель данной научной статьи – описать, как видеоблоги*

применяются для развития навыков устной речи и насколько эффективно их использование при изучении английского языка. Результаты исследования показали, что большинство студентов заинтересованы в использовании социальных сетей для улучшения навыков устной речи на английском языке.

Ключевые слова: *видеоблог, видеоблогинг, навыки устной речи, социальные сети, медийная грамотность.*

RAQAMLI ASRDA YOSHLARNING MEDIA SAVODXONLIGI: INGLIZ TILIDA GAPIRISH KO'NIKMASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA VLOG YURITISHNING O'RNI

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Annotatsiya. *Zamonaviy yoshlar hayotida ijtimoiy tarmoqlarning o'rni beqiyos bo'lib, ularning imkoniyatlari tobora ortib bormoqda. Shu bois, bu platformani ta'limda, xususan, xorijiy tillarni o'rganishda samarali vosita sifatida ishga solish muhim sanaladi. Ijtimoiy tarmoqlar orqali til o'rganish jarayoni nafaqat oson, balki qiziqarli ham bo'lishi mumkin, chunki bu jarayon o'zaro hamkorlik, ijodkorlik va erkin fikr almashinuviga asoslanadi. Shunday vositalardan biri — Vlog yuritish, ya'ni video blog hisoblanadi. Vlog o'quvchilarga dars jarayonini jonli, shaxsiy va mazmunli tarzda tashkil etishga yordam beradi. Bu media vositasi orqali ular o'z fikrlarini erkin bayon etishadi, ingliz tilida so'zlashishga bo'lgan ishonchni oshiradilar hamda nutq ko'nikmalarini mustahkamlashga intiladilar. Ushbu ilmiy maqola aynan vloglardan foydalanish orqali ingliz tilida so'zlashuv malakasini rivojlantirish jarayonini yoritadi. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, aksariyat talabalar ijtimoiy tarmoqlar yordamida ingliz tilida muloqot qilish imkoniyatidan mamnun bo'lib, bu yo'nalishga katta qiziqish bilan yondashmoqdalar.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Video blog, vlog yuritish, gapirish ko'nikmasi, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar, media savodxonlik.*

I. Introduction

As technology is developing faster than ever, it has drastically altered the way people connect and share information shaped by the internet. The advent of social media demonstrates the latest chapter in the continuous evolution of human communication. Social media has redefined the boundaries of time and space, allowing

for immediate global communication and the formation of virtual communities that go beyond geographical restrictions. Social media refers to a group of online platforms that enable users to share content, collaborate, engage with others through activities such as posting, commenting and interacting with one another. There are lots of different types of social media including social networking sites, online forums, sharing photos and videos, writing reviews, blogs and vlogs.

Since the emergence of social networking platforms in the early 2000s, particularly in 2002, social media has gained immense popularity and become an integral part of daily life for millions of people worldwide. Platforms like Facebook, Instagram and Twitter allow users to maintain relationships with friends and family, share life updates and engage in real-time conversations. Whether it is a forum for discussion of a specific topic or a professional network, this has opened new opportunities for collaboration and learning. Besides, #Booktok (60.8 billion views) on Tic Tok, for example, is all about literature, with users sharing their passion for books with millions and boosting sales of previously unknown authors, while #Fintok is doing the same for financial education. Over on Twitter, teens find access to political debates and can become politically informed while watching debates unfold¹.

However, in today's digital age, young people are not just passive consumers of content but also active creators. In this case, media literacy has become an essential skill for today's youth, equipping them with the ability to critically analyze, create and engage in digital content in a responsible and informed way. A recent report shows that 71 % of teenagers state social media gives them a space to express their creative side². This shift opens new possibilities for skill development, particularly in language learning. One notable trend is vlogging, a form of video blogging, which enables youth to express themselves, engage with global audiences and enhance their English-speaking skills in real-world contexts. This article explores how vlogging, as a part of youth media engagement, serves as a powerful pathway to develop both media literacy and English language proficiency.

1 This information was originally published on <https://www.gohenry.com>

2 This insight was shared by psychologist and freelance writer Mendy French in 2023.

II. Related research

Many studies have been carried out on vlogging projects and they have consistently demonstrated the effectiveness of vlogging activity to improve students' speaking skill. Here are a few notable examples:

- One study, titled "Increasing Students' Talk Time through Vlogging", was conducted by Jon Watkins from Kwansai Gakuin University in Hyogo, Japan. It was held in two universities in Japan. The result showed that vlogging can improve students' talk time.

- Another study, “Top-Up Students' Second Language Talk Time through Vlogs”, was led by Dr. Beena Anil, an Assistant Professor in the Department of English at SDNB Vaishnav College for Women in Chromepet, Chennai, India. The findings indicated that vlogging allowed students to study at their own pace, made the English learning process enjoyable.

III. Discussion

A. Learning English through Social Networks

English is among the most in-demand languages globally. In many countries, including ours, English has become an essential part of a learning curriculum and its importance continues to grow in line with digital communication. Since gaining independence, the demand for learning English in our country is creating numerous opportunities for young people to study English language. The integration of social networks into the teaching and learning process is still ongoing. And its role is invaluable in learning a foreign language as well as English. In what ways social media support learning English language? Primarily, engaging in conversations through comments, messages and even on voice and video calls on social media platforms like Telegram can significantly improve spoken English skills. By actively participating in discussions about a particular theme, learners practice forming sentences, expressing ideas. Another positive side is that on platforms like Instagram or Tic Tok users can find challenges and take part in where they are required short videos in English on specific topics. Moreover, watching videos on video-sharing educational platforms like YouTube can offer learners grammar lessons and authentic conversations. Language learning apps also allow learners to find native English speakers to practice communication. Ultimately, to actively practice speaking and writing, students can create their own content. This can reinforce to build self-assurance in using the language publicly.

B. Vlogging for developing English speaking skills

Speaking has been widely recognized as a vital language skill and has received vast attention in English as a foreign language (EFL). Despite the focus and importance placed on teaching of speaking across various educational contexts, it remains as one of the most challenging language skills for most of the EFL learners. Learners, especially, those at the beginner-levels feel afraid of making mistakes and feel unconfident when they have to speak in front of people. In the context of Uzbekistan, professors face some challenges when teaching English as a foreign language. As for teachers, the challenge of teaching speaking to EFL learners could be attributed to a few pedagogical reasons, such as expecting to teach all language skills within limited contact time and large class size. As a result, this issue highlights the need to create more individualized speaking opportunities for learners. One way to overcome above-

mentioned limitations is to increase their speaking time outside the classroom. However, significant obstacle to this approach is that many EFL students lack the social support, for instance, group of peers who can engage in English language conversations with them. Fortunately, the development of innovative technologies potentially fulfil the need for out of class speaking opportunity. In this regard, Videoblog (vlog) comes with the idea providing a tool to ease students' speaking abilities.

C. What is Vlog?

Vlogging has grown in popularity among all generations as one of the most popular daily digital videos. It is a mix of the words "video" and "blog" that allows users to create, upload and watch lifestyle videos. Most people that have vlogs talk about a variety of things, such as hobbies, tips, short speeches and so on. Fiddan & Debbag (2018) stated that if a blog is a written piece of information shared on a website, a vlog is a creative video that anybody may make and edit creatively as they like (adding photos, sounds and text), then publish or share on social media platforms such as YouTube, Facebook, and others.

D. How Vlog improves students' speaking skill?

Students can choose any media hosting that they think will be suitable for the content they want to share in their vlogs. By creating mini-vlogs, students practice speaking about various topics such as their daily lives, studies, social activities, or hobbies in English. This helps them express their thoughts more freely and naturally. Step-by-step methods to improve speaking skill through vlogging:

Topic selection:

Students start by choosing the topic they are passionate about or familiar with. This reduces anxiety and encourages to speak confidently. For example, a student may start her Instagram story with "First, my morning coffee and a quick review of yesterday's notes!".

Script writing:

Before recording students write a short script or outline in English. This step helps them organize their ideas. Example script caption: "Hi everyone! In today's vlog, I'll share my top 3 tips to stay productive during exam week!"

Practice speaking:

Students rehearse multiple times to improve fluency and pronunciation. They can record themselves and listen back to identify areas of improvement. Many young learners commonly use friendly, conversational expressions like:

- "I feel like..."
- "Let me show you..."
- "This is so aesthetic!"

- “Can’t wait to share this with you guys.”
- “Here’s a quick tip...”

These expressions help them sound more natural and confident in English

Recording the vlog:

Using smartphone, students record their vlog. The act of speaking to camera builds confidence and reduces fear of public speaking.

To make sure that this media works effectively, viewers, especially, teachers and students’ friends should be encouraged to give positive comments that can motivate the students to produce better results to train their communication skill. There are also some limitations regarding poor Internet connection, especially in remote places. The problem can be solved by playing the vlog offline. On the other hand, students tend to spend too much time on creating it. As teachers, it is important to set deadlines so that students will be aware of when they are expected to submit or upload their videos.

Nowadays, many students in Uzbekistan have also become celebrities due to their ability to create interesting vlogs that can attract viewers to become their what so called as “subscribers”. Recent studies in Uzbek universities have shown that students who vlog regularly improve their speaking skills by 20-30%.

E. The Role of Media Literacy in Vlogging

Media literacy is the ability to access, analyze, evaluate and share media in various forms. When young people engage in vlogging, they naturally develop and apply these skills. Vlogging teaches students how to use digital tools (camera, editing apps, platforms like YouTube or Instagram). For instance, adding subtitles, editing for clarity, or using hashtags shows understanding of how digital content works. After posting a vlog, students often get comments, likes, or messages. They learn to read them carefully and respond politely. If someone says, “Your sound is too low,” the student fixes it in the next vlog. Furthermore, when students plan a vlog, they think critically about their message, audience, and format. They decide what to say, how to say it, and which visuals/audio to include. This strengthens their ability to create purposeful, well-structured content which is a core of media literacy skill.

IV. Observation & Results

During the first semester, the first-year English-major students were given as a home assignment to create and share a process paragraph using English language. As part of this task students were encouraged to present their work through Instagram stories. Students were free to choose their own topics which led to a variety of creative and personalized contents, like the process of making traditional Uzbek dish, steps to do a specific hairstyle, how to organize a study desk and so on. By explaining these processes in English and recording them as Instagram Stories, students practiced using time-order transitions such as first, then, next and finally; choosing visuals, background

music and layout to make their content more engaging; overcome hesitation to speak in English on a public platform.

V. Conclusion

Based on the discussion and result above, it can be concluded that Vlogging as an alternative oral communication strategy for improving English speaking skill has proven to be a fun and easy-to-access media. It also offers opportunities for digital literacy skills and multilingual peer learning. Teachers should also keep up with the advancement of technology so that they will not be left behind as compared to the students. If teachers can create this kind of situation in teaching and learning process, then there will be no doubt that the result of learning will be as expected.

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